

BIR O'LCHOVLI STEFAN MASALASI

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ABSTRACT

Now we will construct the simplest form of mathematical model describing phase transitions. The classic Stefan problem is a solidification and melting problem, such as the transition between ice and water. To obtain a solution to the classical Stefan problem, the heat equation must be solved. As mentioned above, it is needed to obtain a unique solution. It is called the variable "Stefan condition" and given below.

Keywords: soil, phase, freezing temperature, thermal conductivity.

1. INTRODUCTION

O'zgaruvchan noma'lum interfeys $x = s(t)$ sifatida belgilanadi, bu erda x - fazodagi pozitsiya; $s(t)$ - erkin chegara va t - vaqt. [1]

Stefan shartini olish uchun biz ba'zi taxminlar qilishimiz kerak. O'tishlar sodir bo'lganda, kichik hajmdagi o'zgarishlar bo'ladi, garchi bu erda biz soddalik uchun bu xususiyatni e'tiborsiz qoldiramiz. Fizik sabablarga ko'ra harorat fazalar orasidagi

$x = s(t)$ interfeysida uzluksiz bo'lishi kerak:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow s(t)^+} u_S(x, t) = \lim_{x \rightarrow s(t)^-} u_L(x, t) = u_m \quad \text{barcha } t \text{ uchun} \quad (1)$$

Ikki faza o'rtasidagi o'zgarishlar harorati doimiy qiymatga ega deb hisoblanadi, u_m . Boshlang'ich vaqtda $t = t_0$ $x = s(t_0)$ da ajratilgan ikki xil fazaga ega Ω ni ko'rib chiqamiz, buni 1-rasmda ko'rish mumkin. Biz tekislik simmetriyasini u haroratni faqat t va x ga bog'liq deb qabul qilamiz.

Rasm 1

Ω $x = s(t)$ 2 ta fazaga ajratilgan $\Omega_1 = \Omega \cap \{x < s(t)\}$ va $\Omega_2 = \Omega \cap \{x > s(t)\}$.

Interfeysning o'ngga, ya'ni qattiq erigan paytda holatini faraz qilaylik. Shunday qilib, biz suyuqlik fazasida $u \geq u_m$ va qattiq fazada $u \leq u_m$ bo'lishini kutishimiz kerak.

$t = t_0$ vaqtida interfeysning bir qismini ko'rib chiqing, S maydoni bo'lgan A disk shaklida soddaligi uchun. Keyinchalik $t_1 > t_0$ vaqtida interfeysning o'rnini $s(t_1) > s(t_0)$ ga o'zgartirdi.

Ayni paytda hajmi $S \times (s(t_1) - s(t_0))$ bo'lgan silindr erib ketgan va shuning uchun Q issiqlik miqdorini chiqaradi:

$$Q = S(s(t_1) - s(t_0)) * \rho l \tag{2}$$

Bu yerda l - o'ziga xos yashirin issiqlik va ρ - zichlik.

Issiqlik oqimi

$$\phi_L = -K_L Du_L \tag{3}$$

$$\phi_S = -K_S Du_S \tag{4}$$

Bu erda K_i - $i = L$ va qattiq $i = S$ bo'lgan suyuqlik uchun materialning o'tkazuvchanligi va biz $u \in C^1$ deb qabul qilamiz.

Energiyani tejash orqali (2) tenglamada so'rilgan umumiy issiqlik (5) ga teng deb taxmin qilish tabiiydir,

$$Q = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \int_A [\phi_L * \hat{x} + \phi_S * (-\hat{x})] dAd\tau = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \int_A [K_L Du_L(s(\tau), \tau) * \hat{x} - K_S Du_S(s(\tau), \tau) * (-\hat{x})] dAd\tau, \tag{5}$$

bunda \hat{x} x - yo'nalishidagi birlik vektoridir.

Fazoviy koordinatalar bo'yicha (5) ifodani integrallash

$$Q = A \int_{t_0}^{t_1} [-K_L \frac{\partial u_L}{\partial x}(s(\tau), \tau) + K_S \frac{\partial u_S}{\partial x}(s(\tau), \tau)] d\tau$$

(1.2.6)

buni (2) ifodaga teng deb hisoblaymiz.

(2) va (6) tenglamani tenglashtirib, (7) olamiz.

$$(s(t_1) - s(t_0)) * \rho l = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} [-K_L \frac{\partial u_L}{\partial x}(s(\tau), \tau) + K_S \frac{\partial u_S}{\partial x}(s(\tau), \tau)] d\tau \quad (7)$$

, $t_1 \rightarrow t_0$ chegarasini oling:

$$l \rho \lim_{t_1 \rightarrow t_0} \frac{s(t_1) - s(t_0)}{t_1 - t_0} = \lim_{t_1 \rightarrow t_0} \frac{1}{t_1 - t_0} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} [-K_L \frac{\partial u_L}{\partial x}(s(\tau), \tau) + K_S \frac{\partial u_S}{\partial x}(s(\tau), \tau)] d\tau \quad (8)$$

1 Teorema (Oraliq qiymat teoremasi).

$f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ va $f \in C$ bo'lsin, u holda f $f(a)$ va $f(b)$ oxirgi nuqtalari orasidagi barcha qiymatlarga erishadi.

Isbot. Masalan tomonidan berilgan [2]

2 Teorema (Integrallar Uchun O'rtacha Qiymat Teoremasi).

Agar $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ va $f \in C [a, b]$ da bo'lsa, u holda $c \in [a, b]$ soni mavjuddir

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = (b - a) f(c). \quad (9)$$

Isbot.

1.2.2 teoremadan kelib chiqadiki, uzluksiz $f(x)$ funksiya a ga ega $[a, b]$ oraliqda minimal qiymat m va maksimal qiymat M . Integrallarning monotonligi va $m \leq f(x) \leq M$ dan kelib chiqadiki,

$$mI = \int_a^b m dx \leq \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq \int_a^b M dx = MI \quad (10)$$

bunda

$$I = \int_a^b dx = b - a \quad (11)$$

(11) tenglamadan foydalanilganda va (10) tenglamada I ga bo'linganda ($I > 0$ bo'lsa) (12) hosil bo'ladi.

$$m \leq \frac{1}{b - a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq M \quad (12)$$

Ekstremal qiymat teoremasidan bilamizki, m va M ga ham integral kamida bir marta erishiladi. Shuning uchun Oraliq qiymat teoremasi f funksiyasi $[m, M]$ dagi barcha qiymatlarga ega ekanligini aytadi, aniqroq u $c \in [a, b]$ mavjud.

$$f(c) = \frac{1}{b - a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \quad (13)$$

2 teorema yordamida biz (8) tenglamani

$$l \rho s'(t_1) = \lim_{t_1 \rightarrow t_0} \frac{1}{t_1 - t_0} * (t_1 - t_0) f(c) \quad (14)$$

shaklida yozishimiz mumkin, bunda biz yangi funktsiyani (soddalik uchun) (15) kiritdik. $c \in [t_0, t_1]$.

$$f(c) = -K_L u_x(s(c), c) + K_S u_x(s(c), c) \quad (15)$$

. Lekin $t_0 \rightarrow t_1$ va f uzluksiz ($u \in C$) bo'lgani uchun

$$l\rho s'(t_1) = f(t_1)$$

(16)

ga teng bo'ladi.

Shu bilan birga, xuddi shu protsedura t_1 o'rniga istalgan vaqtda bajarilishi mumkin bo'lganligi sababli, biz (17) ni yozishimiz mumkin va shuning uchun f uchun ifoda bilan biz (18) ga erishamiz, bu Stefan sharti deb ataladi va erkin chegaradagi chegara shartidir. [3].

$$l\rho s'(t) = f(t) \quad (17)$$

$$l\rho \frac{ds}{dt} = K_L u_x(s(t), t) - K_S u_x(s(t), t) \quad (18)$$

Bir o'lchovli bir fazali muammoni yarim cheksiz qattiq jism sifatida ko'rsatish mumkin, masalan, qotib qolish harorati $u = 0$ bo'lgan $0 \leq x < \infty$ ni egallagan yupqa muz bloki. Qattiqlashuvdagi har qanday hajm o'zgarishiga e'tibor bermaslik kerak bo'lgan taxmin. Yupqa muz blokining belgilangan chegarasida $x = 0$ u yerda $f(t)$ ko'p turli xil "oqim funksiyalari" bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, biz qattiqlashuv haroratidan yuqori bo'lgan doimiy haroratga ega bo'lishimiz mumkin, ya'ni $u_0 > 0$, yoki vaqtga bog'liq funksiya. Biz taxmin qilamizki, harorat qattiq faza doimiy bo'ladi. Shunday qilib, muammo suyuqlik fazasida harorat taqsimotini va erkin chegara $s(t)$ o'rnini topishdir. Ikki faza mavjud bo'lsa ham, muammo bir fazali muammo deb ataladi, chunki bu faqat suyuqlik fazasi noma'lum.

Suyuqlik hududi,

$$0 \leq x < s(t)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{K_L}{C_L \rho} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \alpha_L \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$$

Issiqlik tenglamasi $0 < x < s(t)$, $t > 0$,

$$u(0, t) = f(t),$$

Chegaraviy shart, $t > 0$,

$$u(x, 0) = 0,$$

Boshlangich shart

Erkin chegara

$$x = s(t)$$

$$\rho l \frac{ds}{dt} = -K_L \frac{\partial u}{\partial x},$$

Stefan sharti

$$s(0) = 0,$$

Eritma interfeysining dastlabki holati,

$$u(s(t), t) = 0,$$

Interfeysdagi Dirixlet holati,

ya'ni muzlash harorati

2-faza - qattiq hudud,

$$s(t) < x < \infty,$$

$$u(x,t) = 0 \quad t, x \geq s(t) \quad (19)$$

$x = 0$ chegara sharti har qanday bo'lishi mumkin,
ammo bunda biz [4] ga amal qilamiz va quyidagi holatlarni ko'rib chiqamiz:

(i) $f(t) = 1$

(ii) $f(t) = e^t - 1$ (20)

Aslida ikkala muammomizni [4] ga muvofiq hal qilish mumkin edi.

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